

PERFORMANCE OF GRAPHENE/EPOXY DIAPHRAGM HEADPHONES

Hsien-Kuang Liu¹, Y. K. Cheng²

^{1,2} Department of Mechanical and Computer Aided Engineering, Feng Chia University, Taichung, 40744 Taiwan, ROC, ¹ hkliu@fcu.edu.tw, ² sz6505@gmail.com

Keywords: Graphene oxide paper, Composite, Lined pattern, Curved pattern

ABSTRACT

Goal of this paper is to fabricate innovative diaphragm headphones using graphene oxide paper (GOP) and GOP/epoxy composites (GOPC). Initially, graphene oxide suspension is fabricated, and the vacuum filtration method is adopted to make GOP. Then vacuum bag molding is used to fabricate GOPC from GOP. Performance of GOP and GOPC diaphragm headphones are analysed based on their sound pressure level (SPL) curves. There are four important parameters that will influence performance of diaphragm, including material type GOP versus GOPC, the composite diaphragm with lined (GOPC-L) or curved (GOPC-C) patterns, sonication time on suspension, and graphene weight fraction in suspension.

Results show that the GOP diaphragm headphone possesses a wider bandwidth and smoother SPL curve in lower frequency range, while the GOPC diaphragm headphone has comparative smoother SPL curve in higher frequency range. Pattern indentations on GOPC can significantly improve SPL performance of the GOPC diaphragm headphone in the lower frequency range, and performance of GOPC-L is better than GOPC-C. Effects of sonication time and graphene weight fraction on SPL of GOP and GOPC headphones are in reverse, and this is associated with different stacking, compliance and interlayer bonding of GOP and GOPC diaphragms, respectively. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) observation of both diaphragms are examined, and correlation between previous three factors and SPLs of GOP and GOPC is proposed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene, the one-atom thick strong bonded carbon membrane, exhibits intriguing electronic, thermal, mechanical, and optical properties. By stacking a few layer graphene nanosheets, the material becomes graphene papers (GPs). GPs can preserve most properties that the monolayer graphene possesses. Dikin et al. [1] initially fabricated GO (graphene oxide) paper from GO water solution by vacuum filtration method. The GO paper has tensile strength of 120 MPa. Suk et al. [2] first fabricated monolayer graphene by CVD method, and then transferred this graphene film onto PET as graphene/PET composite film to be a loudspeaker. A thermoacoustic effect is transferred from the composite film to surrounding air and sound wave is created, and sound pressure level (SPL) of this film is around 50 dB. Xu [3] found that the piezoelectric PVDF film can be sandwiched by two graphene layers. Once the voltage is applied on graphenes, reverse piezoelectric effect can lead to vibration of PVDF film and sound waves are created. Kim et al. [4] used nitrogen doped reduced graphene oxide arrays (N-rGOA) to make a thermoacoustic array loudspeaker.

Based on the literature review, graphene papers are excellent diaphragm candidates for acoustic devices due to their high stiffness and low mass. Aim of this paper is to fabricate graphene oxide paper (GOP) from well dispersed graphene oxide (GO) nanosheets water suspension using the vacuum filtration method. Besides, graphene oxide paper/epoxy composites (GOPC) are fabricated by vacuum bag molding method. Then both graphene oxide paper (GOP) and GOP/epoxy composites (GOPC) with GO weight fraction of 26% are adopted as diaphragms in the electromagnetic headphones. In addition, lined pattern (GOPC-L) and curved pattern (GOPC-C) indentations are molded onto both surfaces of the diaphragm by hot-press molding. Therefore, there are four important parameters affecting performance of diaphragm, including material type, GOP versus GOPC, pattern type on composite line or curve, sonication time (T1~3), and graphene weight fraction in solution (WF1~3).

Sound pressure level (SPL) curves of GOP and GOPC diaphragm headphones are analyzed by the soundcheck measurement system. SEM is used to observe microstructure of both GOP and GOPC diaphragms.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Graphene oxide (GO) is fabricated by modified Hummers method [5]. First, 12 gram expanded graphite powders are added to 460 ml H_2SO_4 and the suspension is stirred in an ice bath. Later, 60 gram $KMnO_4$ are slowly added to the suspension and heated to 35 °C and stirred for 2 hours. Then 920 ml deionized water is slowly added the suspension and the temperature has to be kept under 50 °C. The suspension is further diluted in 2800 ml deionized water, and then 50 ml 30% concentration H_2O_2 is added. The suspension stands still for 24 hours. The suspension is initially set in centrifuge by revolution of 6000 rpm for 1 hour to separate solute and solvent. The solute is further purified as GO by the addition of mixture of water and methanol. The centrifuge and purification processes are repeated for several cycles.

GO papers (GOP) are fabricated by vacuum filtration method. GO suspension is poured into upper container of a vacuum filtration apparatus. Lower bottle has an outlet that connects with a vacuum pump. There is a filtration assembly consisting of porous glass and cellulose filter paper between upper and lower parts of the apparatus. When the vacuum pump is turned on, solvent of the GO suspension is sucked out and GO nano platelets are combined as GOP above filtration assembly. After drying process, a free stand circular GOP with diameter 35 mm can be achieved. In order to get GOP/epoxy composites (GOPC), first a GOP is soaked into epoxy resin at 60°C for one hour. Then the soaked GOP covered by release fabrics is placed inside a vacuum bag, and a vacuum pump is connected to outlet of the bag and started up. At the same time, the vacuum bag is placed inside an oven at 60°C for 4 hours to cure the epoxy. After the curing process, GOPC diaphragm is achieved.

In order to clarify effect of processing parameters on acoustic performance of various GOP and GOPC diaphragms, table 1 shows terminology for various fabricated diaphragms. Sonication times on suspension T1, T2, T3 are 1, 5, 10 minutes, respectively; GO weight fractions in suspension WF1, WF2, WF3, are 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 wt%, respectively; pattern type on composites are lined (L) and curved (C) indentations, respectively.

To prepare a GOP diaphragm headphone, a plastic ring frame is adhered on edge surface of GOP. Then a dynamic voice coil is adhered on opposite surface of the GOP, and centers of both voice coil and GOP must be aligned. Further, this diaphragm is assembled with a headphone unit consisting of a yoke, a magnet, and a PCB. Positive and negative electrodes of the dynamic voice coil are connected to the corresponding electrodes of PCB, and the headphone is ready for testing. The preparation procedure for the other three diaphragm headphones is similar.

The headphone is tested inside the anechoic chamber. An amplifier is connected to the headphone and sound waves in the frequency range from 100 to 20k Hz are created. The sound waves are detected by a microphone. The amplifier and microphone are connected to a computer with Soundcheck software, and the SPL (sound pressure level) curve of the graphene diaphragm headphone is measured. To measure compliance of the diaphragm, the set-up of the measurement system is similar to that for SPL, except the microphone is replaced by a laser measurement system.

Diaphragm type	Sonication time on suspension (min)	GO weight fraction in suspension (wt%)	Pattern type on composite
GOP	T1 (1)	WF1 (0.5)	Lined (GOPC-L)
(Graphene oxide paper)	T2 (5)	WF2 (1.0)	Curved (GOPC-C)
GOPC	T3 (10)	WF3 (1.5)	
(GOP/epoxy composite)			

Table 1: Terminology for various graphene diaphragms.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of material type

Figure 1 shows SPL (sound pressure level) curves for diaphragm headphones fabricated by GO papers (GOP), GOP/epoxy composites without pattern (GOPC), and with curved (GOPC-C) and lined (GOPC-L) patterns. All GO paper diaphragms are fabricated with GO weight fraction 1.5 wt% (WF3) in solution and with sonication time 10 minutes (T3). At frequency response lower than 3000 Hz, The GOP-T3-WF3 (GOP) diaphragm has smoother SPL curve than the other three diaphragms, GOPC-T3-WF3, GOPC-C-T3-WF3, and GOPC-L-T3-WF3. Besides, GOP possesses largest bandwidth and in the frequency range from 350 to 3.5k Hz the SPL curve is above 90 dB, which indicates that its sensitivity is good. This is due to higher mechanical compliance of GOP. Highest SPL value for GOP is 98 dB at first resonant frequency 430 Hz, which is better than 50 dB in reference [2]. For the composite GOPC with lower mechanical compliance (higher stiffness), first resonant frequency shifts to higher frequency around 1800 Hz, compared with GOP, and its bandwidth is smallest.

Figure 2(a) and (b) depicts micrographs for cross sectional views of both GOP-T3-WF3 and GOPC-T3-WF3 diaphragms, respectively. As shown in figure 2(a), highest weight fraction WF3 would lead to thick and almost uniform stacked GO nanosheets. Only few interlaminar pores are found at right hand side of the micrograph. Interlaminar holes still exist for GOPC as shown in figure 2(b), and this indicates that there is very little epoxy infiltration. Since the GOPC is fabricated by vacuum bag molding, epoxy is very difficult to infiltrate in the through-thickness direction via tortuous pores of the GOP.

Figure 1: SPL curves for diaphragm headphones fabricated by GO papers (GOP), GOP/epoxy composite without pattern (GOPC), and with lined (GOPC-L) and curved patterns (GOPC-C).

Figure 2: Micrographs of diaphragms (a) GOP-T3-WF3, (b) GOPC-T3-WF3.

3.2 Effect of pattern on composite

Figures 3(a) and 3(b) depicts respectively fabricated composite diaphragm headphones with lined (GOPC-L) and curved (GOPC-C) patterns. Both patterns are uniform short line or arc indentations in the radial direction. Figure 1 also shows effect of pattern type of composite on SPL curves for both diaphragm headphones. With pattern on composite diaphragms, first resonant frequencies of both GOPC-C and GOPC-L shift back to lower frequency range due to their medium mechanical compliance; besides, it is found that both patterns on GOPC can significantly improve SPL performance of the GOPC diaphragm headphone in the lower frequency range because compliances of patterned GOPC are higher than that of GOPC. In the high frequency range larger than 3000 Hz, all four diaphragms depict unstable SPL curves; however, GOPC-C shows a relative smoother SPL curve. Table 2 shows compliance of various diaphragm headphones. GOP-T3-WF3 possesses highest compliance of 7.25 m/N, while with patterns GOPC-L and GOPC-C have medium compliances, and GOPC has lowest compliance of 0.30 m/N. Compared with GOPC-C, GOPC-L has wider bandwidth in lower frequency range due to its higher compliance. Furthermore, SPL performance of GOPC-L with compliance 1.14 m/N is better than that of GOPC-C with compliance 0.88 m/N in the low frequency range, because lateral vibration mode of the former is the major vibration mode shape.

Figure 3: Photographs for fabricated patterned composite diaphragm headphones, (a) GOPC-L, and (b) GOPC-C.

T3-WF3	Compliance C_{ms} of various diaphragm headphones			
	GOP	GOPC	GOPC-L	GOPC-C
C_{ms} (m/N)	7.25	0.30	1.14	0.88

Table 2: Compliance of various diaphragm headphones.

3.3 Effect of sonication time

Figure 4 shows SPL curves for GOP diaphragm headphones fabricated by various sonication times T1~T3 applied in suspension. For lower sonication time T1, the bandwidth of diaphragm GOP-T1-WF3 seems to extend to lower frequency of 300 Hz; besides, in the frequency range from 1k to 7kHz, GOP-T1-WF3 also indicates a comparatively smoother curve but lower dBs. With lower sonication time T1, the size of 2D GO nanosheets is larger, and when GO nanosheets combine as GOP, they tend to be a loose stacking, but those larger nanosheets can interlock together. On the other hand, for GOP-T3-WF3 with higher T3 there is a tight packing of smaller GO nanosheets in the GOP with intrinsic small pores indicated by figure 2(a). Upon frequency sweeping by SPL measurement in the high frequency range, those pores may lead to oscillation of the SPL curve.

Figure 5 depicts SPL curves for GOP/epoxy (GOPC) diaphragm headphones fabricated by various sonication times. Trend of effect of sonication time on SPL for GOPC is in reverse compared with that for GOP. GOPC-T3-WF3 has wider bandwidth at lower frequency and smoother curve at higher frequency than GOPC-T1-WF3. Fabricated by T3, GOP is stacked by smaller sized 2D GO nanosheets, and pores inside GOP is less tortuous in the through-thickness direction. Upon fabricating GOPC, epoxy resin is easier to infiltrate GOP. This results in better interlayer bonding of GOPC-T3-WF3 as well as better SPL performance.

Figure 4: SPL curves for GO paper diaphragm headphones fabricated by various sonication times on suspension

Figure 5: SPL curves for GOP/epoxy diaphragm headphones fabricated by various sonication times on suspension

3.4 Effect of graphene weight fraction

Figure 6 illustrates SPL curves for GOP diaphragm headphones fabricated by various GO weight fraction in suspension. According to our studies, higher weight fraction of WF3 can lead to thicker GOP with higher compliance which results in the headphone with larger bandwidth around 500 Hz and smoother curve around 10k Hz, but lower SPL level around 85dB, compared with that by WF1. In contrast, figure 7 depicts different trend of effect GO weight fraction in suspension on SPL curves for GOPC diaphragm headphones, compared with figure 6. Lower weight fraction of WF1 can lead to thin GOP. Later when GOPC is fabricated from GOP, epoxy resin is easier to infiltrate the GOP. This results in better interlayer bonding of GOPC-T3-WF1 as well as its better SPL performance, compared with GOPC-T3-WF3.

Figure 6: SPL curves for GO paper diaphragm headphones fabricated by various GO weight fraction in suspension.

Figure 7: SPL curves for GOP/epoxy diaphragm headphones fabricated by various GO weight fraction in suspension.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, four kinds of diaphragm headphones are fabricated including GOP (graphene oxide paper) GOPC (GOP/epoxy composites), GOPC-L (lined pattern GOPC), and GOPC-C (curved pattern GOPC) headphones, and their SPL performance is investigated. Results show that the GOP diaphragm headphone possesses a wider bandwidth and smoother SPL curve in lower frequency range, and its highest SPL value is 98 dB at first resonant frequency 430 Hz. On the contrary, the GOPC diaphragm headphone has comparative smoother SPL curve in higher frequency range and highest SPL value of 100 dB. It is found that both patterns on GOPC can significantly improve SPL performance of the GOPC diaphragm headphone in the lower frequency range because compliances of patterned GOPC are higher than that of GOPC. Further, SPL performance of GOPC-L with compliance 1.14 m/N is better than that of GOPC-C with compliance 0.88 m/N in the low frequency range, because lateral vibration mode of the former is the major vibration mode shape.

Lower sonication time T1 results in better SPL of GOP-T1-WF3, but worse SPL of GOPC-T1-WF3 headphone in the lower frequency range. Result of the former headphone is caused by the stacking of interlocked larger sized 2D GO nanosheets, while result of the latter is caused by worse infiltration of epoxy resin during GOPC composite fabrication. Higher graphene fraction WF3 leads to better SPL of GOP-T3-WF3, but worse SPL of GOPC-T3-WF3 headphone in the lower frequency range. Result of the former headphone is caused by higher compliance; while result of the latter is caused by worse infiltration of epoxy resin in thick GOP as well as worse interlayer bonding during GOPC fabrication. Due to different fabrication features of GOP and GOPC, effects of sonication time and graphene weight fraction on their SPLs are in reverse. To sum up, GOP and GOPC diaphragms can be highly potential candidates for headphones applied in lower and higher frequency ranges, respectively. Imitating a coaxial speaker, GOP and GOPC diaphragms can be combined into a high performance headphone.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is financially supported by Ministry of Science and Technology, Taiwan (MOST 107-2221-E-035-059).

REFERENCES

- [1] D.A. Dikin, S. Stankovich, E.J. Zimney, R.D. Piner, G.H.B. Dommett, G. Evmenenko, S.T. Nguyen and R.S. Ruoff, Preparation and characterization of graphene oxide paper, *Nature*, **448**, 2007, pp. 457-460.
- [2] J.W. Suk, K. Kirk, Y. Hao, N.A. Hall, R.S. Ruoff, Thermoacoustic sound generation from monolayer graphene for transparent and flexible sound sources, *Advanced Materials*, **24**, 2012, pp. 6342-6347.
- [3] S.C. Xu, B.Y. Man, S.Z. Jiang, C.S. Chen, C. Yang, M. Liu, X.G. Gao, Z.C. Sun, C. Zhang, Flexible and transparent graphene-based loudspeakers, *Applied Physics Letters*, **102**, 2013, pp 151902.
- [4] C.S. Kim, K.E. Lee, J.M. Lee, S.O. Kim, B.J. Cho, J.W. Choi, Application of N-doped three-dimensional reduced graphene oxide aerogel to thin film loudspeaker, *ACS Applied Materials Interfaces*, **8**, 2016, pp. 22295-22300.
- [5] H.K. Liu, Y.C. Wang, T.H. Huang, Moisture effect on mechanical properties of graphene/epoxy nanocomposites, *Journal of Mechanics*, **32**, 2016, pp. 673-682.